

CHARACTERIZATION OF MODE II FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF ANGLED LAMINATE INTERFACES

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ABSTRACT

A cracked laminate beam test has been used to investigate the dependence of mode II fracture toughness of aligned fibre composites on the relative ply orientation of the plies constituting the interface. Beam analysis and two dimensional finite element analysis (FEA) have been conducted to evaluate specimen compliance and strain energy release rates. FEA confirmed the beam prediction of the mode II fracture nature of the test geometry. Numerical examples have shown that the agreement of specimen compliances and strain energy release rates by the two analyses varies with specimen lamination. Tests have been performed on a carbon fibre/epoxy resin T300/914C composite. Experimentally measured specimen compliances compared well with the FEA results. Mode II fracture energies of angled interfaces have been derived using both analyses, and found to increase slightly with the relative ply angle. Fractographic investigation revealed a correlation between the increase of energy and the fracture surface morphology.

KEY WORDS: Delamination fracture; Fracture toughness; Strain energy release rate; Laminated plate theory; Finite element analysis (FEA); Scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

1. INTRODUCTION

The damage tolerance of fibre reinforced composites for aerospace use is often evaluated by post impact compression strength. Examination of impact damage in cross ply[1] and quasi-isotropic laminates[2] has shown that delamination damage, which controls residual compressive performance, tends to develop between laminae of different orientations. It has also been shown that delamination caused by both impact[3] and post impact compression[4] is predominately mode II fracture (forward shear). Therefore an improved insight into delamination between angled plies is vital to toughening strategies[5] for this class of materials.

Delamination between aligned plies has been investigated widely. There have also been a number of studies addressing both mode I and mode II delamination between angled plies[6-10]. From a review of these publications two important issues appear to warrant further examination, i.e., a) the design of a test geometry that promotes a pure mode II fracture between laminae of different orientations, and b) the establishment of a data reduction scheme for evaluating fracture energy. These are investigated in the present paper using a cracked beam flexural test [11].

2. ANALYSIS OF $G_{IIc}(\theta)$ TEST

Figure 1 shows the cracked laminate beam test used in the present investigation. It is based on the central notched flexural (CNF) test[12] which has recently been extended to consider off mid-plane delamination propagation and angle ply laminates[11]. A complete derivation of a beam solution of the energy release rate and compliance for cracked beams conforming to a balanced lamination restraint was derived in [11]. Formulae relevant to the present investigation are summarised in the Appendix. A simple stacking sequence $[(+\theta/-\theta/0_12/-\theta/+\theta)/(-\theta/+\theta/0_12/+\theta/-\theta)]$ ($\theta = 0^\circ, 7.5^\circ, 15^\circ, 22.5^\circ, 30^\circ, 37.5^\circ, 45^\circ$) was chosen in this investigation to study the dependence of mode II interlaminar fracture toughness on the relative angle (2θ) of the interface (hereafter referred to as the $G_{IIc}(\theta)$ effect). The dimensions of the cracked beam used in the tests and analyses were 135mm long ($2L$) and 20mm wide (W).

Fig. 1-- Cracked laminate beam model ($2L=135.0mm, 2h = 4.32mm, W=20.0mm$)

Fig. 2-- Finite element model for cracked laminate beam ($P=1.0 N, W=1.0 m$) (only half of the beam modelled due to symmetry, unit load and beam width chosen)

2.1 Beam Solution of $G_{IIc}(\theta)$ Test The two sublaminates of the cracked region are both symmetric with respect to their own mid-surfaces. Although not exactly symmetric, the uncracked beam is shown by stiffness matrices of laminate plate theory to be quasi-symmetric, i.e., the twisting effect can be neglected. Thus, in the following, the beams are treated as symmetric, with the principle in-plane and bending stiffness denoted by A_{11} and D_{11} . From equations (a.5) in the Appendix (Shear correction for all the beams are assumed to be the same.)

$$\left(\frac{1}{A}\right)_u = \left(\frac{1}{A}\right)_L = \frac{1}{A_{11}} \quad \left(\frac{1}{B}\right)_u = \left(\frac{1}{B}\right)_L = 0 \quad \left(\frac{1}{D}\right)_u = \left(\frac{1}{D}\right)_L = \frac{1}{D_{11}}, \quad \left(\frac{1}{S}\right)_u = \left(\frac{1}{S}\right)_L = \frac{1}{S_{55}} \quad (1)$$

and from equations (a.4)

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{1}{\tilde{A}}\right)_u &= \left(\frac{1}{\tilde{A}}\right)_L = \frac{1}{A_{11}} + \left(\frac{h}{2}\right)^2 \frac{1}{D_{11}}, & \left(\frac{1}{\tilde{D}}\right)_u &= \left(\frac{1}{\tilde{D}}\right)_L = \frac{1}{D_{11}} \\ \left(\frac{1}{\tilde{B}}\right)_u &= -\frac{h}{2} \frac{1}{D_{11}}, & \left(\frac{1}{\tilde{B}}\right)_L &= \frac{h}{2} \frac{1}{D_{11}}, & \left(\frac{1}{\tilde{S}}\right)_u &= \left(\frac{1}{\tilde{S}}\right)_L = \frac{1}{S_{55}} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where h is the height of the sublaminate. From equations (a.3) the combined stiffness terms of the cracked beam system are arrived at,

$$\frac{1}{A} = 2 \left(\frac{1}{A_{11}} + \left(\frac{h}{2} \right)^2 \frac{1}{D_{11}} \right), \quad \frac{1}{B} = 0, \quad \frac{1}{D} = 2 \frac{1}{D_{11}}, \quad \frac{1}{S} = 2 \frac{1}{S_{55}} \quad k = 1 \quad (3)$$

The force resultants of the sublaminates at the crack tip can now be obtained by substituting equations (1) - (3) into equations (a.2) (Note that the shear terms have vanished),

$$N_u = -N_L = - \frac{A_{11}}{D_{11} + \left(\frac{h}{2} \right)^2 A_{11}} \frac{h}{4} a \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{b}{a} \right) \frac{P}{w}$$

$$Q_u = Q_L = - \frac{1}{2} \frac{P}{W}, \quad M_u^*(0) = M_L^*(0) = - \frac{b}{2} \frac{P}{W} \quad (4)$$

The uncracked beam moment and stiffness M_t and \bar{D}_t in equation (a.1) can be expressed as:

$$M_t = -b \frac{P}{W} = 2 M_u^*(0), \quad \bar{D}_t = 2 \left(D_{11} + \left(\frac{h}{2} \right)^2 A_{11} \right) \quad (5)$$

The bending moments of the sublaminates relative to their own mid-planes at the crack tip can be found using equations (4) and (a.2):

$$M_u = M_L = M_u^*(0) - \left(\frac{h}{2} \right) N_u \quad (6)$$

Substituting (1) - (5) into equation (a.1), the strain energy release rate can be solved:

$$G = \frac{M_u^2}{D_u} - \frac{M_u^*(0)^2}{D_t} + \frac{N_u^2}{A_{11}} \quad (7)$$

Using equation (6), the energy release rate expression (7) is finally reduced to

$$G = \frac{1}{16} \frac{1}{D_{11} \left(1 + \left(\frac{2}{h} \right)^2 \frac{D_{11}}{A_{11}} \right)} \frac{P^2 a^2}{W^2} \quad (8)$$

The compliance of the specimen can be obtained using equation (8) as detailed in [11], this reads (V is the central deflection of the beam under load $2P$):

$$C = \frac{V}{2P} = \frac{1}{12WD_{11}} \frac{1 + \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{h}{2} \right)^2 \frac{A_{11}}{D_{11}} \left(\frac{a}{L} \right)^3}{1 + \left(\frac{h}{2} \right)^2 \frac{A_{11}}{D_{11}}} + \frac{3}{10} \frac{1}{G_{13}Wh} \quad (9)$$

2.2 Finite Element Analysis of GIIC(θ) Test To investigate the accuracy of the beam prediction of equations (8) and (9), a finite element analysis has been performed. Based on the same argument in section 2.1 that validates the adoption of the two dimensional beam analysis, a two dimensional plane strain four node iso-parametric finite element was used to simulate the beam in the x-y plane (see Fig. 1). To reduce computational cost, the angle plies in the beam were modelled by an equivalent modulus obtained through stiffness transformation. Version HP9000 of a general purpose finite element package MARC (K3) was used to perform the analysis.

A typical finite element mesh is shown in its deformed configuration in Figure 2. The virtual crack closure method by Rybicki and Kanninen[13] was adopted for the evaluation of the strain energy release rates of the beam system with the application of high stiffness springs at crack

tip nodes. Contact between the cracked sublaminates at the delamination was simulated by the introduction of tying constraints that enforce an equality of the sublaminata transverse displacements of corresponding nodes at the delamination.

The five sets of material properties shown in Table 1 were used in the investigation. Material property Set 0 in the table was experimentally measured data obtained in the present investigation. The other four sets of material properties are from other sources on the same material system, and they were used to investigate the influence of material properties on the precision of the beam prediction. Table 2 lists the equivalent flexural moduli of the angle plies used in the FEA, which were obtained using equation (6.20) in [14] for off-axis elastic properties.

Table 1 Material properties for computation (all units in GPa)

Material set	0	1	2	3	4
G12	5.11	1.96	3.60	6.40	1.96
G13	1.96	1.96	3.60	6.40	6.40

Note: For all the material sets the following properties are assumed, $E_{11}=127.5\text{GPa}$
 $E_{22}=8.7\text{GPa}$ and $\mu_{12}=0.33$.

Table 2 Equivalent flexural moduli for angle plies by transformation (all units in GPa)

θ	0°	7.5°	15°	22.5°	30°	37.5°	45°
material 0	127.5	122.03	103.69	74.42	46.29	27.79	17.88
material 1	127.5	121.53	100.27	64.45	31.56	23.85	7.43
material 2	127.5	121.79	102.12	69.98	39.74	21.50	13.08
material 3	127.5	122.23	104.93	77.80	51.25	32.66	21.71

Note: Material Set 4 has the same flexural modulus as 1 and is not listed in the table.

The results by the virtual crack closure method (denoted Gvcc) are compared to those by compliance difference method (denoted Gcd) in Table 3 (Note that data presented for the FEA are based on unit load and width unless otherwise specified). The computations were based on two different mesh divisions with the sides of the square elements around the crack tip being $1/32$ and $1/64$ (designated af32 and af64) of the whole beam height $2h$. The stability of both the compliance and strain energy release rates as shown in the table, in conjunction with their rapid convergence revealed in a gradual mesh refinement study (not reported here due to limitation of space), clearly validates the af32 mesh arrangement of the FEA model. All the results given below are based on the mesh shown in Figure 2 (af32 mesh).

Table 3 Results of one-step mesh convergence study using material 3

Mesh	DOF	Compliance(10^{-6} m ² /N)		GII vcc (10^{-7} J/m)		G cd (10^{-7} J/m)	
		0°	45°	0°	45°	0°	45°
af32	4208	2.03038	2.87996	0.4858	1.0313	0.4880	1.0373
af64	13742	2.03453	2.88696	0.4935	1.0518	0.4925	1.0510

Note: GIvcc tends to zero in all the cases.

2.3 Comparison of Beam and FEA Predictions Beam and FEA predictions for specimens with a relative cracked length of $a/L = 0.4$ were obtained and compared using the material property Set 0 in Table 1. Beam prediction of the compliance of the half beam is

dictated by equation (9), with the second term reflecting the effect of transverse shear. It was found from all the computations of the cracked beam FEA results that the crack closure method consistently produced a mode II delamination fracture as predicted by the beam model. Figure 3 shows the results of the two predictions for material Set 0. For specimen compliance (Fig. 3(a)) beam prediction with transverse shear deformation compares better with FEA than bending alone. As θ increases, the discrepancy between the FEA and beam predictions in both compliance and strain energy release rate grows rapidly. The minimum discrepancy occurs at $\theta=0^\circ$ (Fig. 3(a), (b)).

(a) Compliance results

(b) Strain energy release rate results

Fig.3-- Comparison of predictions using measured material properties ($P=1N$, $W=1m$)

To identify the reason for the somewhat unexpected disagreement between the beam compliance and energy release rate predictions, a parametric study was conducted to examine the influence of material properties. Figure 4 shows the results of calculations based on material property Sets 1, 2, 3 and 4. It is seen from the results for material Sets 1, 2 and 3 that increases in G_{12} and G_{13} , which produce a decrease of the transverse shear deformation and through beam height non-uniformity, lead to a decrease in the discrepancy between the two predictions. A comparison of the results for material Sets 1 and 4 illustrates that transverse shear is not the primary source for the disagreement in beam compliance prediction (Fig. 4(a)), but it does affect the energy release rate result as shown in Figure 4(b), which is contrary to the beam prediction that only A_{11} and D_{11} influence the energy release rate.

(a) compliance comparison

(b) energy release rate comparison

Fig. 4-- Comparison of beam and FEA predictions for different material sets

3. EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Testing Procedures A single layer 5 μm thick PTFE film was embedded into Ciba-Geigy T300/914C carbon/epoxy laminates as a delamination crack starter during the hand lay-up process. Specimens with ply angles θ from 0° to 45° (7.5° increments) were tested. As in [11, 12] a precrack procedure was employed to create a sharp delamination front beyond the resin rich region that existed at film tips. Precracked specimens were then tested on a three point bending test rig in a screw driven 50 kN capacity test machine with a cross-head speed of 1mm/min. The load-displacement response of the specimens was recorded during the tests. Generally the specimen behaved linearly until a small region of nonlinearity appeared on the load displacement trace. This was followed by a sudden load drop that corresponded to an unstable delamination fracture. This behaviour was very similar to that reported for the ENF tests[15], and as in the reference, two critical loads, nonlinear and maximum loads (denoted P^{Lin} and P^{Max}), were used in the toughness evaluation. After failure, the specimens were peeled apart to measure the initial precrack length directly from the fracture surface; a change of appearance on the delamination surface enabled an accurate measurement. Some specimens were further examined by scanning electron microscopy(SEM).

3.2 Test Results The specimens failed by delamination propagation from one end of the precracks to the point of the outer roller support of the test rig. Examination of the fracture surfaces revealed two types of macroscopic failure. The first type occurred in specimens with lamination angles not over 30° . Pure delamination propagated at the precrack front. The second type occurred in specimens with higher lamination angles and involved transverse cracks and multiple delaminations. The compliances of specimens with θ equal to 0° , 7.5° , 22.5° and 45° were measured before precracking, and the results are shown in Figure 5 together with those predicted by beam and FE analyses by using material property Set 0. P^{Lin} and P^{Max} measured from the load displacement curves are listed in Table 4. Using these loads and equation (8), the change of fracture toughness with the ply angle θ was obtained and this is shown in Figure (6).

Table 4 Range of precrack length, critical loads and number of specimens tested

Orientation.	0°	7.5°	15°	22.5°	30°	37.5°	45°
a/L range	0.44--0.63	0.53--0.59	0.46--0.48	0.55--0.58	0.47--0.55	0.51--0.58	0.48--0.51
P^{Lin} (N)	1070--1740	1208--1580	1506--1740	1190--1325	1190--1500	1190--1340	1190--1307
P^{Max} (N)	1120--1780	1326--1676	1506--1820	1210--1380	1232--1680	1240--1420	1330--1440
Num. Spec.	10	9	8	10	8	8	9

Since the precrack produced varying initial precrack lengths, accurate prediction of fracture toughness using FEA requires expensive individual computations corresponding to each crack length. To avoid the computational cost, a scaling procedure for an estimation of fracture toughness as shown by equation (10) was used to examine the trend of the toughness changes with the angle. These results are also shown in Figure 6.

$$G^{\text{FEA}} = \left[\frac{G^{\text{FEA}}}{G^{\text{Beam}}} \right]_{\theta/L=0.4} G^{\text{Beam}} \quad (10)$$

Fig 5-- Comparison of compliance results (W=20.0mm)

Fig. 6-- Fracture energy based on critical load measurements (W=20.0mm)

3.3 Fractography

Regions just ahead of the precrack on the delamination fracture surfaces were examined by scanning electron microscope to identify possible changes of fracture surface morphology. Typical results are shown in Figure 7. The areas examined were believed to be associated with the first occurrence of the nonlinearity, and therefore, they should be associated with the linear fracture toughness results in Figure 6.

Fracture occurred mainly in the resin phase, since bare fibres were rarely seen by SEM (Fig.7(a)(b)(c)(d)). Fracture of angled interfaces showed larger regions of resin deformation as a result of the existence of resin rich grids between the two angle plies (Fig. 7(b)(c)(d)). Another feature revealed by SEM is the position of fibre resin debonding. Fibre matrix interfacial failure occurred in random positions in unidirectional specimens (Fig. 7(a)). For the angled interfaces, especially for low relative angles, fibre resin debonding was concentrated at places where the fibres in the different laminae intersected.

It was also found that in specimens with θ higher than 30° , micro cracks along fibre direction appeared (Fig. 7(d)). This was clearly a result of the presence of off-fibre axis shear stresses in the angle plies.

4. DISCUSSION

The disagreement between the beam and FEA predictions for specimens with small lamination angles suggests that beam prediction gives low estimates of the compliance and strain energy release rate. A similar result has been observed for other types of mode II fracture test[16]. While the exact reason for the discrepancy between the beam analysis and FEA for specimens with higher angles remains to be ascertained, numerical examples suggest that it results from the modelling of the highly non-uniform laminations.

On the experimental side, pure delamination fracture has obtained in specimens with θ equal or less than 30° . Increasing θ from 0° to 30° resulted in only a small increase in G_{IIc} . Fractography revealed an increased extent of resin deformation and regularly arranged regions of fibre matrix debonding at fibre overlapping positions of angled interfaces. Hence the small increase in G_{IIc} with θ did correspond to a change in observed fracture surface morphology.

Fig. 7-- SEM micrographs showing fracture surfaces of specimens with different relative angles at mid-surface
(a) $\theta=0^\circ$ (b) $\theta=7.5^\circ$ (c) $\theta=22.5^\circ$ (d) $\theta=45^\circ$

Similar tests on fabric reinforced composites showed a more pronounced dependence of G_{IIc} on relative ply angle [8], but no link between G_{IIc} , ply angle and fracture micromechanism was reported. Increasing θ from 30° to 45° produced a further increase in G_{IIc} . This corresponded to the observed intralaminar and multiple delamination failure which would account for the increased fracture energy.

5. CONCLUSIONS

- (1) Beam analysis predicts correctly the mode II nature of the $G_{IIc}(\theta)$ test. Beam predictions of specimen compliance and strain energy release rate are in reasonable agreement with FEA for low lamination angles.
- (2) Tests on T300/914C showed that the test geometry promoted pure mode II delamination for specimens with ply angles up to 30° . For this category of specimens only a small increase of mode II fracture energy with relative ply angle was found.
- (3) For specimens with ply angles over 30° , intralaminar and multiple delamination fracture occurred which corresponded to a measured increase of fracture energy with θ .
- (4) In general, for angled interfaces additional resin deformation and regular fibre matrix interfacial fracture were observed, compared to delamination of the unidirectional composite.

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Appendix: Summary of beam formula for cracked beam model

A detailed derivation of the beam formula for the cracked beam model can be found in [11], and the results used in this work are summarised here with the original equation numbering in reference [11] cited.

Energy release for the beam is (eq. (18) of [11])

$$G = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{M_u^2}{\bar{D}_u} + \frac{M_L^2}{\bar{D}_L} - \frac{M_L^2}{\bar{D}_t} + \frac{N_u^2}{A_u} + \frac{N_L^2}{A_L} + 2 \frac{N_u M_u}{B_u} + 2 \frac{N_L M_L}{B_L} \right) \quad (a.1)$$

where \bar{D}_t and M_t are total bending stiffness and moment of the uncracked beam at the crack tip position. In equation (a.1) N_u , N_L and M_u , M_L are crack tip axial forces and bending moments of the upper and lower sublaminates relative to their own mid-planes, which are given by the following equations (eq. (12) of [11]).

$$\begin{aligned} N_u &= -k \left[\frac{A}{\bar{B}_L} \left(1 - \frac{\bar{B}_L \bar{D}_L}{B D} \right) \right] a \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{b}{a} \right) \frac{P}{W} & N_L &= -k \left[\frac{A}{\bar{B}_u} \left(1 - \frac{\bar{B}_u \bar{D}_u}{B D} \right) \right] a \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{b}{a} \right) \frac{P}{W} \\ Q_u &= -\frac{(c_s)_L}{c_s} \frac{\bar{D}}{\bar{D}_L} \frac{P}{W} & Q_L &= -\frac{(c_s)_u}{c_s} \frac{\bar{D}}{\bar{D}_u} \frac{P}{W} \\ M_u^*(0) &= k \left\{ -\frac{b}{a} \frac{\bar{D}}{\bar{D}_L} + \frac{AD}{BB_L} \left[\frac{b}{a} + \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{c_s} \frac{\bar{B}_L \bar{D}_L}{B D} \right) \right] - \frac{c_s - 1}{2 c_s} \left(-\frac{1}{k} \frac{S}{\bar{S}_L} + \frac{\bar{D}}{\bar{D}_L} \right) \right\} \frac{P}{W} & & \\ M_L^*(0) &= k \left\{ -\frac{b}{a} \frac{\bar{D}}{\bar{D}_u} + \frac{AD}{BB_u} \left[\frac{b}{a} + \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{c_s} \frac{\bar{B}_u \bar{D}_u}{B D} \right) \right] - \frac{c_s - 1}{2 c_s} \left(-\frac{1}{k} \frac{S}{\bar{S}_u} + \frac{\bar{D}}{\bar{D}_u} \right) \right\} \frac{P}{W} & & \end{aligned} \quad (a.2)$$

$$M_u^* = M_u + \frac{h_u}{2} N_u, \quad M_L^* = M_L - \frac{h_L}{2} N_L$$

$$k = -\frac{B^2}{AD-B^2}, \quad c_s = 1 + \frac{12D}{a^2 S}, \quad (c_s)_u = 1 + \frac{12\tilde{D}_u}{a^2 \tilde{S}_u}, \quad (c_s)_L = 1 + \frac{12\tilde{D}_L}{a^2 \tilde{S}_L}$$

A, B, D in equation (a.2) are stiffness terms for the cracked beam system defined by (eq. (13) in [11]),

$$\frac{1}{A} = \frac{1}{\tilde{A}_u} + \frac{1}{\tilde{A}_L}, \quad \frac{1}{B} = \frac{1}{\tilde{B}_u} + \frac{1}{\tilde{B}_L}, \quad \frac{1}{D} = \frac{1}{\tilde{D}_u} + \frac{1}{\tilde{D}_L}, \quad \frac{1}{S} = \frac{1}{\tilde{S}_u} + \frac{1}{\tilde{S}_L}. \quad (a.3)$$

The stiffness elements are related to individual sublaminates stiffnesses by the following two sets of equations, with $[A_{11}]_k$, $[B_{11}]_k$ and $[D_{11}]_k$, $k=u, L$ following definitions in laminate plate theory.

$$\frac{1}{\tilde{A}_u} = \frac{1}{A_u} - h_u \frac{1}{B_u} + \left(\frac{h_u}{2}\right)^2 \frac{1}{D_u}, \quad \frac{1}{\tilde{D}_u} = \frac{1}{D_u}, \quad \frac{1}{\tilde{A}_L} = \frac{1}{A_L} + h_L \frac{1}{B_L} + \left(\frac{h_L}{2}\right)^2 \frac{1}{D_L}, \quad \frac{1}{\tilde{D}_L} = \frac{1}{D_L},$$

$$\frac{1}{\tilde{B}_u} = \frac{1}{B_u} - \left(\frac{h_u}{2}\right) \frac{1}{D_u}, \quad \frac{1}{\tilde{S}_u} = \frac{1}{S_u}, \quad \frac{1}{\tilde{B}_L} = \frac{1}{B_L} + \left(\frac{h_L}{2}\right) \frac{1}{D_L}, \quad \frac{1}{\tilde{S}_L} = \frac{1}{S_L} \quad (a.4)$$

$$\left[\frac{1}{A}\right]_k = \left[\frac{D_{11}}{A_{11}D_{11}-B_{11}^2}\right]_k, \quad \left[\frac{1}{B}\right]_k = \left[-\frac{B_{11}}{A_{11}D_{11}-B_{11}^2}\right]_k, \quad \left[\frac{1}{D}\right]_k = \left[\frac{A_{11}}{A_{11}D_{11}-B_{11}^2}\right]_k, \quad \left[\frac{1}{S}\right]_k = \left[\frac{1}{S_{55}}\right]_k. \quad (a.5)$$

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